

- ▲ archaeological site
- border
- river
- capital
- turquoise mines
- REGION

DEM: Natural Earth 2 v3.2
 Admin: The World Bank
 Hydro: Natural Earth, OSM, RIMES

Projection: WGS 1984
 Datum: WGS 1984

